

Path2Integrity questionnaire for students without an academic degree (undergraduates)

Instructions

During this evaluation, we kindly ask you to respond to the following 5 case scenarios about research practices. Each case scenario starts with a short description followed by 4 steps which build on one another. Only one option can be chosen for each question.

First decide which action is in line with good research practices and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please choose a reason for your answer by choosing the option that best suits your opinion and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please note that you cannot return to a previous page of the survey! But you may always skip a question, stop the survey, or withdraw from it completely.

Sam saw that Richard had falsified data in a research project. Sam wants to follow good research practices and thus informs the ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- police.
- public relations office.
- ombudsperson.
- ethics committee.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sam's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it is Sam's duty.
- it ensures an equal treatment of all misconduct cases.
- it protects the reputation of his organisation.
- it ensures reliable research results.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Emma, who is new at the university, gets the opportunity to conduct her own small research project. She decides to analyse the feedback from some interviews as part of the project. Since Emma has never been through a research process before, she looks at the relevant guidelines on how to analyse interviews. To follow good research practice, Emma ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- carries out the analysis to the best of her ability and knowledge.
- chooses an appropriate analysis method and then follows its procedural rules.
- chooses a method of analysis to familiarize herself with the general process.
- chooses the method used by most others.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Emma's decision complies with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- in this way, knowledge is gained systematically and logically.
- it corresponds to the fundamental democratic structure of research.
- binding rules hinder innovation.
- it is her duty to follow the guidelines.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

For his first research project at the university, Tim wants to find out how to follow principles of responsible research and what he has to take into account. To follow good research practices, Tim ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- just starts work and learns by doing.
- looks at the university's guidelines for good research practices.
- looks for examples in the press.
- proceeds based on what he has learned in school.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Tim's decision complies with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures reliable research results.
- everyone does it like this.
- research must not be restricted by rules.
- it saves valuable resources.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sarah is in charge of the coordination of a research project. Before the project starts, she has to decide how to handle an agreement on principles for the collaborative working group. To follow good research practices, Sarah ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- draws up an agreement and sends it to all partners with a request for approval.
- makes a draft agreement and sends it to all partners asking for their comments.
- tells the project partners to start and that the agreement will be submitted later.
- informs each group that it is responsible for establishing and adhering to its own principles.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sarah's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- an agreement that is accepted and signed by the partners is the basis for transparency.
- as a coordinator, the general principles of collaborative work are her responsibility.
- it is her responsibility to avoid wasting valuable time.
- the agreement always requires a majority decision.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Marc has to write his term paper for university. Now he is sitting in the library and has already found literature that he wants to use. He remembers that Professor Andrew said something about the importance of citation. To follow good research practices, Marc should use ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- a citation style that is common in his discipline.
- exactly the citation styles of the texts read.
- a citation style he likes.
- no specific citation style.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Marc's decision is in line with good research practices, because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- the majority follows this practice and Marc must too.
- it ensures appropriate presentation of the source and the original author.
- this decision ensures research is treated equally and consistently.
- due to the complexity and variety of research, there can be no binding codes and regulations.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident